

CONCRETE DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING USING COMPUTER VISION

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ABSTRACT

Detecting the early degradation of concrete structures can assist agencies in forecasting and planning future resource demands. Structural defects network SDNET2018 classes were used to create a custom binary convolutional neural network CNN classifier with physical crack damage predictive accuracy of 99.2%. Second, concrete's physical, chemical, and reinforcement damage classes, including a negative class, are stratified to generate a separate dataset using concrete defect bridge image CODEBRIM cropped image database to train a multiclass image classifier model with predictive accuracy of 80%. Comparisons were made based on the computational efficiency of a CNN architecture-specific classifier model and a ResNet50-retrained transfer-learning model predicting at 87.45% accuracy. These findings enable the generalisation and improvement of the damage assessment accuracy of concrete structures.

KEYWORDS

Structural Health Monitoring; Computer Vision; Deep Learning; Convolutional Neural Networks; Concrete damage; Transfer learning; Image classification.

INTRODUCTION

The structural strength, durability, resistance, stability, residual life, and safety can all be affected by deterioration (Sanchez-Silva et al., 2011). Early identification, maintenance, and repair are critical for minimising structural degradation and avoiding the need for comprehensive rehabilitation (Sherif & Smith, 1981). Maintenance aims to reduce costs while improving working conditions over time. This outcome is accomplished by considering physical failures to evaluate safety and serviceability during probabilistic crucial points in a building's lifespan (Frangopol & Soliman, 2016; Zhu & Brilakis, 2010). However, this evaluation can be prone to mistakes or inefficient expenditure use. Inspection and evaluation by competent inspectors and civil engineers helps forecast future conditions, plan investments, and allocate limited maintenance and repair resources to ensure that civil infrastructure satisfies service demands (Monavari, 2019). The wide variation in the nature and spatial characteristics of defects limits human involvement, requiring a predictive degradation detection approach utilising automated inspection systems (Spencer et al., 2019). The vast size of structures can make sensor and actuator instrumentation in dynamic response systems impossible, expensive, and require a well-structured network and on-site computational resources (Sohn & Law, 2000). Thus, the instrumentation defect identification problem is unsolvable or inadequately stated, with infinite alternative solutions requiring normalisation for environmental conditions, live or ambient loads, and the resolution of noise sources that alter measured signals (Feng et al., 2015).

Objectively comparing human visual inspection with computer vision is impossible because of variations in evaluation abilities and experience. Given datasets and weights, deep learning (DL) neural networks can recognise any feature, whereas human visual inspection requires subjective judgement. Dodge and Karam (2017) discovered that although humans and deep-learning neural networks performed equally on a 10-class subset of ImageNet, people were less accurate with noisier pictures than transfer-learning models such as ResNet, InceptionNet, and VGG16. According to He et al. (2016), a residual net built on VGG16 achieved a slightly better accuracy rate than human recognition. Several models are available, including an unsupervised multi-layer neural network

(Sarkar et al., 2016), convolutional neural network (CNN) transfer learning (Azimi & Pekcan, 2020), covariance matrix aware CNN (Seventekidis et al., 2020), long-short term memory and hybrid deep learning-CNN LSTM with stacked autoencoders for crack identification and acceleration data evaluation (Dang et al., 2020), as well as spalling detection on structural parts (Bao et al., 2019; Kang & Cha, 2018). Other studies have investigated the use of a feature pyramid and hierarchical boosting networks (Cha et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019), SVM with SURF (Kim et al., 2019), mask region-based CNN (Kim & Cho, 2019), and depth cameras for volumetric damage measurements and spalling checks (Beckman et al., 2019). Furthermore, a structure from motion technique with object localisation and damage detection has been investigated for rapid post-event visual evaluation of building façades (Choi et al., 2018). Deep transfer learning using VGG and CNN still picture classification has also been investigated for the multi-classification of object recognition, spalling checks, damage degree, and type (Gao & Mosalam, 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Observations suggest that the current computer vision literature on structural damage assessment is diverse and frequently specialised to relevant datasets and study objectives. However, it does not provide a critical evaluation of the efficacy of these techniques in practical applications, examine the limitations and challenges of these methods, or provide practitioners with comparisons. Most importantly, few models use a combinatory classifier approach to evaluate the overall precision and reliability of the damage identification system. Furthermore, most models are used to identify the presence of defects rather than to classify them based on their causes, limiting their practical usefulness in recommending remediation.

The purpose of this study is to create a supervised damage identification model for concrete structures using CNN and computer vision. The objective is to identify appropriate DL neural architecture to distinguish concrete damage classes with minimum pre-processing of images. This paper describes an iterative identification procedure that includes dataset acquisition and filtering, data pre-processing, partitioning validation and training sets, constructing an appropriate architecture, drawing inferences, sample predictions, and overall architecture performance comparisons using batch predictions and metrics. The raw image database used to train the CNN model was obtained from Structural Defects Network SDNET2018 and Concrete Defect Bridge Image CODEBRIM. Based on the Portland Cement Association (2002) deterioration classifications were categorised into physical, chemical, and corrosion of reinforcement metals. The source of damage is critical for determining the best restoration procedure. Accordingly, this study contributes to identifying the cause of deterioration in a deficient area of research.

METHODOLOGY

Data acquisition

The model was trained using opensource image datasets obtained from the Structural Defects Network (SDNET2018) (Maguire et al., 2018) and the Concrete Defect Bridge Image (CODEBRIM) (Mundt et al., 2019). Also, some primary data samples with known outcomes were collected and used to benchmark and tweak the machine-learning algorithms. Originally, the SDNET2018 dataset contained 56000 images, of which 40000 images were used (pre-classified into 20000 positive and 20000 negative images). The binary classification architecture of this study was trained, validated, and analysed for damage identification using 40,000 images (from SDNET) and multi-category classification using 5,532 images (from CODEBRIM) datasets. It is worth noting that the CODEBRIM datasets required more data filtering than the SDNET datasets.

Dataset

SDNET2018 is an annotated picture dataset containing 56,000 positive or negative bridge surfaces, concrete structures, and pedestrian walkways that can be used to train, validate, and benchmark AI-based concrete crack detection methods such as deep learning CNN. Maguire et al. (2018) took 230 16-megapixel full-sized images and divided them into 256 sub-pictures for cracks ranging from 0.06 to 25 millimetres. Shadows, roughness, scale, edges, holes, and background debris were also collected. The CODEBRIM database is essential because it contains more defect classes than the crack-only data. Deep learning must sample the real world to assess visual faults (Mundt et al., 2019). This dataset comprises bridges with fractures, exposed reinforcements, efflorescence,

spallation, chemical corrosion, and no damage. Physical damage is assumed to be caused by abrasion/erosion, volume changes, overload/impact, loss of support and surface defects (Delatte, 2009); chemical damage by acids, salts, alkalis, sulphates, and silica/carbonate reactivity (Zivica & Bajza, 2001); and reinforcement damage by the corrosion of embedded metals. Several cameras at varying magnifications were used to capture wet and discoloured surfaces under various weather conditions. Due to the inaccessibility of bridges, drones captured part of the dataset. Figure 1 shows the manual data filtering to construct the damage class directories of physical, chemical, reinforcement, and no damage to train the model.

Binary and multiple classifiers training

The first model detected the physical damage in concrete using the balanced SDNET2018 subset, which comprises 20,000 positive and 20,000 negative images of concrete cracks. In a ratio of 90:10, the dataset was divided into training and validation sets. The machine learning algorithm divides the dataset into two distinct directories based on the new list lengths. The training dataset was utilised to generate a binary decision rule that prognosticates the unobserved binary labels of new instances from their feature values. Binary classification algorithms based on supervised learning were employed to learn the prediction rules, see Figure 1.

Figure1: Training methodology for classifiers

The multiclass dataset consists of 5532 cropped images obtained from CODEBRIM. The multiclass dataset required filtering of ambiguous and overlapping images to eliminate factors that did not pertain to the four damage classes. A manual process was used to filter and classify the images into four classes for validation and testing. The training and validation subsets were divided at a ratio of 90:10, with physical, chemical, reinforcement, and no-damage training sets containing 1133, 745, 1300, and 1801 images, respectively. The validation set had 200 photos classified as undamaged, 126 images classified as physical damage, 83 images classified as chemical damage, and 144 images classified as reinforcement damage. This dataset was unbalanced owing to the unequal damage distribution in the image source. Numerous CNN models have been developed to derive an accurate representation of datasets. Transfer learning enhanced feature extraction, and two models were explored. The first used an adapted CNN based on Model 1 binary classification, and the second used the ResNet50 transfer-learning model.

Data processing

Kang et al. (2014) advocated resizing all dataset images to 256 by 256 pixels before feeding them into a network to guarantee uniformity. After training, normalisation by dividing RGB colour values by 256 optimises memory and computational needs by rescaling images to preserve pixel values between 0.0 and 1.0. Data augmentation can improve the model's accuracy despite limited data. Sequential model layers with all processes use time domain augmentation to reduce training data. Matching the training and testing distributions reduces the generalisation errors. Scaling, rotation, cropping, contrast adjustment, brightness manipulation, and input layer colour changes are prominent data augmentation methods (Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019). Multiple pre-processing strategies can help convolutional neural networks extract features from complex datasets, but they require more computational power and resources. This study limited pre-processing to vertical and horizontal mirroring and layer rotations.

Model development

TensorFlow is a computational framework that facilitates the movement of multi-dimensional arrays, or tensors, from one node to another along a flowchart (Goldsborough, 2016). It serves as a tool for processing and analysing complex data structures using artificial neural networks. Keras, a high-level neural network API, was created using Python to conduct the tensor operations (Pang et al., 2020). The number of parameters must be kept to a minimum while minimising loss over any tensor network structure (Ran et al., 2020). There is no straightforward method for deciding which decomposition model to apply to most tensor learning issues (Brockmeier et al., 2013). Additionally, the penalty for the incorrect model specification can be high in terms of computational resources and time expenditure. There are no existing algorithms in the literature that apply to this dataset, necessitating exploration and experimentation to find a novel tensor network architecture that would provide the highest accuracy rates while including the appropriate batch sizes, learning rates, training epochs, layers and parameters to minimise the loss of values and resources required for success.

Model architecture

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) extract features from the training set instead of recognising the image and predicting correlations based on the validation set. The feature learning layers include convolution, pooling, and activation layers. The classification layer's fully connected layers and activation layer use the trained weights of the feature-learning layer for prediction (Hussain et al., 2018).

Convolution Layer

The convolution kernel of this layer wraps the input layer to generate a tensor of outputs, making it essential to the CNN (Uchida et al., 2018). Filters activate the inputs. A vector product is used to multiply the filter's input data patch due to its small size. This layer performs the most image computation. The input layer represents images as a 3-dimensional array based on the 2-dimensional image size and RGB colour values, called depth. The fixed filter kernel scans its receptive fields to identify features in the picture. Convolution creates a 2-dimensional image region array. The model uses an arbitrary number of convolutional layers to add depth to the feature map. Multiple convolution layers make CNN networks hierarchical (Gu et al., 2018). Because the subsequent layers recognise the pixels inside the receptive fields of the preceding layers, the output accuracy is improved. The CNN network quantifies the images in the convolution layer.

Pool Layer

This layer independently generated an equal number of combined feature maps from each feature map and was used to lower layer sample input data spatially by taking a maximum value across an input window. Pooling operations sweep a weightless filter across the input, similar to a convolution layer. Pooling extrapolates the aggregate array (Brownlee, 2019).

Activation Layer

Each neuron multiplies its input data by weight and adds the consequences to produce a numerical output. This output determines whether the activation function activates a process in response to a stimulus or not. Activation functions help neurons make decisions (O'Shea & Nash, 2015).

Fully Connected Layer

The fully connected CNN layers store the trained parameters of the model. FC layers require many trainable parameters to fit sophisticated nonlinear classifier functions in the feature map into which the input data items are mapped. With many parameters, the classifier can be overfitted. In multiclass problems, functions such as SoftMax assign decimal probabilities to each class to normalise the output array (Kabani & El-Sakka, 2016). The decimal probability must be 1.0. SoftMax function (multiclass logistic regression).

Transfer learning

Transfer learning involves applying previously learned characteristics to similar settings (Gao & Mosalam, 2018). This method is used when a dataset is insufficient for training a full-scale model.

The process involves freezing the model layers to prevent data loss during subsequent training cycles. Trainable layers are added to the frozen layers to help the model predict new datasets based on past characteristics. Finally, the model (or part of it) is unfrozen and retrained on new data with a low learning rate. The model's performance may be improved by gradually adapting the trained features to new data. Configuring and choosing sufficient hyperparameters (such as batch size, learning rate, and training epoch) takes time, and no specific optimisation recommendations exist. Thus, the best network design for concrete damage detection must be determined through trial and error guided by validation set errors (Yamashita et al., 2018).

ANALYSIS

Binary image classification analysis-model 1

Utilising the partitioned test set from the SDNET database, the features to be extracted mainly consist of physical crack damage. The final classification will have the labels “Crack detected” and “No crack detected”, see Figure 2. The Input layer has variably sized cropped RGB images and is pre-processed using TensorFlow functions to normalise the data by resizing to 256 x 256 pixels, rescaling RGB values to 0.0 to 1.0, and adding 0.2 rotations and horizontal and vertical mirroring iterations of the same image. Due to the balanced dataset and low variance, the following CNN Architecture was computed over 5 batches and trained over 10 epochs. The model was then compiled using the Adam optimiser function and the Accuracy metrics. Sparse categorical cross-entropy was used as the loss function. The results are presented in Table 1.

Figure 2: Architecture for binary classification using custom CNN

Multiclass image classification analysis

The CODEBRIM dataset was partitioned with 90% of the dataset used for testing to train both models for analysis. The features targeted for the training were organised into four classes: Physical Damage, Chemical Damage, Reinforcement damage and Negative (No damage). Owing to the high variance, overlap of multiple damage types and conflict in cumulative damage, the number of prediction classes was restricted to the four categories named above to achieve higher accuracy and successful execution of the model.

Model 2: Custom CNN

Based on a series of trials and errors, the architecture shown in Figure 3 was derived from the results with the highest accuracy rates based on the computational and time constraints. The input layer has variably sized cropped RGB images pre-processed using TensorFlow functions to normalise the data by resizing to 256 x 256 pixels, rescaling 3 RGB channel values to 0.0 to 1.0, and adding 0.1 rotations and horizontal and vertical mirroring iterations of the same image. Because of the complex dataset and high class variance, the CNN architecture was computed over 15 batches and trained over 50 epochs. The model was then compiled using the Adam optimiser function and the accuracy metrics. Sparse categorical cross-entropy was used as the loss function. See Table 2.

Model 3: ResNet50 Transfer learning model

The aim of transfer learning is to use the feature learning layers of ResNet50 that has been trained to categorise a different problem from the one it was built for. We avoid having to retrain a portion of the network by making use of the patterns that the neural network discovered to be helpful when classifying photos of a certain problem to categorise concrete damage. Visual characteristics are

convolved in a typical manner by the frozen pre-trained layers. The other pre-trained layers will be trained on the CODEBRIM dataset, and their weights will be reassigned to the predictions made by the fully connected layer. This transfer learning model was computed over 15 batches and trained over 10 epochs. Details of retrained layers for concrete multi-category classification are as follows. The first layer uses Flatten function to flatten all its input from the previously frozen layers into a single level dimension. The second layer uses a fully connected layer which consists of 512 neurons and a ReLU activation function. The final layer uses the Dense function with 4 nodes and Softmax activation function. The model is then compiled using the Adam optimiser function and Accuracy metrics. Sparse Categorical Cross Entropy is used as the loss function. See Table 1.

Figure 3: Architecture for multi-category classification using custom CNN

Table 1: Metric summary of model 1 and model 3 analysis

Model 1 Binary CNN classifier					Model 3 ResNet50 Transfer learning model			
Epoch	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Training Loss	Validation Loss	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Training Loss	Validation Loss
1	89.55	98.27	0.2333	0.0491	79.36	84.18	2.1219	0.5136
2	97.93	98.35	0.0681	0.0566	89.94	80.91	0.325	0.7153
3	98.46	98.55	0.0518	0.0498	94.26	84.36	0.2036	0.714
4	98.39	98.72	0.0576	0.0398	95.48	87.45	0.1545	0.6637
5	98.61	98.95	0.0469	0.0287	93.88	85.27	0.3116	0.6287
6	98.68	98.90	0.0556	0.0298	97.33	86.18	0.1121	0.6406
7	98.97	98.87	0.0343	0.0342	98.09	85.45	0.0868	0.778
8	98.99	99.18	0.0351	0.0267	96.73	86.55	0.1249	1.0308
9	98.99	99.20	0.0345	0.0261	97.29	86	0.1084	0.9372
10	99.12	99.08	0.0320	0.0303	98.51	85.27	0.0556	1.2172

RESULTS

Model 1: Binary classification using custom CNN model

The binary model, trained over 10 epochs and a batch size of 5 using the normalised and augmented SDNET2018 dataset, reaches a 99.12% accuracy in epoch 10 and a high validation accuracy in epoch 9. The training loss decreases to nearly 0.032, but that validation loss gradually decreases with minimal oscillation but within the range of 0.026 to 0.03 and a global minimum of 0.0261 in validation loss. Overall, we observe a decrease in loss which is a sign of the model creating good predictions. Ideally, the model would be trained over large epochs to make accurate assumptions, but we can observe outliers of a converging model from the plotted graphs. The model performs well since the training and validation accuracy are beginning to overlap and plateau at high accuracy. The training and validation loss curve also converges with minimal loss values, proving that the predicted model is a good fit. The acquired weights in training Model 1 are referenced to provide predicted classes and confidence values for the following batch predictions. Figure 5 is a plot of 10 images from the training subset partition with its original class and inference values. All the images show accurate predictions with high confidence values to validate that we have built a successful model to classify the SDNET2018 dataset. This binary image classification CNN can accurately distinguish images containing physical cracks in concrete from images with no concrete damage. See Figures 4 and 5.

Model 2: Multi-Category Classification using Adapted CNN model

The following results have been obtained by a training set filtered and processed from the CODEBRIM dataset to classify four classes of physical, chemical, reinforcement and no damage. The model contains architecture expanded from Model 1 and the appropriate parameters for completeness. This model is trained over 50 epochs with a batch size of 15 and reaches the highest training accuracy of 80.36% at epoch 46 and the highest validation accuracy in epoch 47 at 80%. The training loss gradually decreases from 1.159 to 0.509. Similarly, a validation loss ranging from 0.935 to 0.543 and a global minimum of 0.5281 was achieved.

Table 2: Metric summary of model 2 analysis

Epoch	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Training Loss	Validation Loss	Epoch	Training Accuracy (%)	Validation Accuracy (%)	Training Loss	Validation Loss
1	49.88	56.36	1.1596	0.9352	26	77.35	72.18	0.5547	0.6428
2	58.01	58.91	1.0282	0.9196	27	76.24	76	0.5887	0.6032
3	62.83	68	0.8739	0.7745	28	78.15	77.82	0.5493	0.5778
4	65.36	66.36	0.8106	0.773	29	78.53	74.91	0.5461	0.6315
5	66.87	63.82	0.7701	0.8019	30	77.59	76.36	0.5516	0.5809
6	67.53	68.18	0.7794	0.7309	31	77.85	78.18	0.544	0.559
7	68.17	69.27	0.7391	0.7498	32	77.89	78.55	0.5452	0.5774
8	68.71	69.45	0.729	0.6973	33	77.79	78.55	0.5369	0.5484
9	70.22	67.45	0.7028	0.7446	34	77.99	79.27	0.5307	0.5594
10	69.88	71.64	0.6929	0.6814	35	76.99	79.82	0.5506	0.5338
11	71.43	72	0.6725	0.6908	36	78.43	74.55	0.5236	0.5751
12	71.18	70	0.6754	0.7415	37	78.21	76.55	0.5369	0.5925
13	73.15	71.64	0.6438	0.709	38	78.35	78	0.5506	0.5914
14	73.49	73.64	0.635	0.6329	39	78.19	77.82	0.5295	0.5342
15	74.42	73.45	0.6262	0.6635	40	79.28	77.45	0.5086	0.5522
16	74.24	74.55	0.6189	0.6199	41	78.71	64.73	0.5372	0.8532
17	75.26	74.36	0.5997	0.6857	42	78.25	77.09	0.5429	0.5824
18	74.72	75.27	0.6098	0.6143	43	79.24	78.36	0.5083	0.5336
19	75.54	75.64	0.604	0.63	44	78.63	76.91	0.5167	0.5719
20	76.67	73.64	0.5748	0.6284	45	78.98	77.82	0.5268	0.5663
21	76.06	75.64	0.5822	0.6604	46	80.36	79.09	0.4943	0.552
22	75.38	71.45	0.601	0.6956	47	79.3	80	0.5093	0.5349
23	76.81	77.09	0.5784	0.5966	48	80	78.55	0.4965	0.5501
24	76.59	76.55	0.5672	0.6025	49	79.88	78.55	0.4958	0.5281
25	76.43	77.09	0.5779	0.5597	50	79.76	78.36	0.5094	0.5439

The stable loss reduction indicates a learning model that fits well with the relative hyper-tuning required for lowering the global minimum. It is observable that the accuracy curves are on an upward trend to convergence but have not fully reached optimum accuracy levels. The loss curves, with minor fluctuations of values, are equally decreasing, which suggests that the CNN architecture with adjustments can achieve greater results. The spikes in the curves can result from mislabelled, hard-to-recognise features and inappropriate parameters. Overall, the model tends to read as a slightly underfit model (Zhang, Zhang and Jiang, 2019). The results in Figure 7 display most images classified accurately, with a relatively satisfactory confidence percentage.

Model 3: Multi-Category Classification using Transfer learning CNN model

This model uses the training subset derived from the CODEBRIM dataset to classify four classes of Physical, Chemical, Reinforcement and No damage as Model 2. This model uses ResNET50 as its base model to retrain for this classification using the transfer learning procedure trained over 10 epochs with a batch size of 15. The model reaches the highest training accuracy and validation accuracy in epoch 10 and epoch 4 with 98.51% and 87.45%, respectively. Early stopping was

incorporated into the model due to a reduction in simulation accuracy for continued evaluation. The training loss is minimised, with the global minimum occurring in epoch 10 with a loss of 0.0556. However, the global minimum for the validation loss occurs immediately in the first epoch with 0.5136 and on an upward trend. This is typically the case of an overfitted model that performs well on the training set but fails to recognise new images within the validation set comprehensively. The source of this discrepancy is regarded as likely due to the complexity and overlap of concrete damage (Pothaganti, 2018). The accuracy curves tend to begin to flatline and slightly deviate between training and accuracy models indicating overfitting and proof of the significant complexity of the current dataset. The upward deviation in the trajectory of the loss curve confirms the high bias rates to translate the training predictions onto the validation dataset.

Figure 4: Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss curves over time for Model 1

Figure 5: Binary classification results for Model 1

Figure 6: Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss curves over time for Model 2

When working with an overfitted model, the literature suggests applying regularisation techniques to minimise loss scores and implementing early stopping procedures. These measures prevent the model from overfitting the training data and enhance its generalisation ability. Figure 8 predictions contradicted the overfitting identified. Albeit this concerning indicator, the batch prediction can successfully predict any image from the training set with extremely high confidence rates. Overfitting

in a model is typical of a complex dataset with low training data or too many classes (Pothuganti, 2018), and in the case of this data set, overlapping features make the model derive fewer training features. The success is owed to the pre-trained model with fine-tuned weights, retrained over this specific classification to make it easier to compute and handle complex datasets and easily extract features (Tammina, 2019).

Figure 7: Multi-category classification results for model 2

Figure 8: Training and Validation Accuracy and Loss curves over time for Model 3

Limitations

A well-planned infrastructure inspection process can aid in developing a structural health monitoring prediction model, but the model's accuracy is contingent on the training data available. The study's limitations prevented further optimisation of the multi-category classification model; however, future work can enhance the model's efficacy via early hyperparameter optimisation. In addition, damage-sensitive features can be extracted using unsupervised learning to improve precision. This study focusses on structural integrity and degradation levels, future studies can address object/element identification or semantic segmentation and recommend appropriate retrofit methods.

Figure 9: Multi-category classification results for model 3

CONCLUSION

Monitoring structural health through visual inspection is the most cost-effective method for preventing unanticipated expenses related to structural integrity. Our research employed computer vision, specifically image classification through convolutional neural networks, to evaluate and categorise various forms of concrete deterioration. Our custom CNN model obtained a validation accuracy of 99.2% for the binary classification of concrete physical damage and 80% for the multi-category classification of four classes of concrete damage. Using ResNet50, we obtained highly precise predictions with a validation accuracy of 87.45%. This paper's methodology, thorough analysis, and recommendations enable us to scale this damage assessment model to multiple target groups, building materials, and building types. To improve the precision of our model, we propose employing object recognition and semantic segmentation. Regarding data acquisition quality, we propose the use of innovative techniques, such as CCTV, handheld or tandem digital cameras, UAVs, 3D mapping with laser scanners, and Internet of Things (IoT) integration, to monitor the structural integrity of buildings and maintain a damage register or database as a streaming source for training and validating assessment algorithms via unsupervised learning. Systems for structural health monitoring will employ entirely automated learning models. Achieving a balance between overfitting and underfitting, variance, and bias exchange is crucial when selecting the proper hyperparameters. It is preferable to adjust the sample size rather than learning rates. The test loss that occurs during network training can be used to determine the optimal network design and hyper-parameters without requiring a full training session to evaluate the network's overall performance. In addition, regulation operations, such as dropout and decay functions, can enhance the equilibrium. This study concludes with a comprehensive methodology for evaluating various forms of concrete degradation for different causes of damage. This study provides a reliable, scalable, and cost-effective method for visual inspection-based monitoring of structural health. By utilising computer vision techniques and automated learning models, professionals in the field are provided with a methodology to make informed decisions, prevent unanticipated costs, and ensure the structural integrity of structures over the long term.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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